

Resilience Beyond Food Production

- Trade and Supply Chains in the Nuclear Winter Context

Ram Eirik Glomseth, September 2023

Abstract

This report explores the emerging field of research on trade and supply chains in the context of nuclear winter scenarios (NWTSC). Through literature review and expert interviews, it is revealed that NWTSC is severely understudied despite the critical role of global food systems and systemic risk in assessing the impacts of a moderate nuclear winter. The report underscores the necessity of transdisciplinary collaboration and systems thinking to understand complex interconnections. The first part examines the historical and current status of NWTSC research through a literature review and expert elicitation on ongoing projects. The second part highlights key considerations for future NWTSC research. Politico-economic factors like state capacity and incentives are analysed as drivers of resilient TSC. Geographic specificity is also emphasised, noting vulnerabilities like pinch points in supply chains. Multidisciplinary perspectives from fields like disaster risk reduction, psychology, and history are suggested to conceptualise systemic risks. The report lays a qualitative foundation to disentangle the intricate dynamics involved in NWTSC. It provides conceptual tools from diverse disciplines to illuminate this existential risk, contributing to emerging modelling projects on nuclear winter scenarios. With rising nuclear tensions, understanding NWTSC and the associated systemic risks is critical. Transdisciplinary inquiry and systems analysis can uncover complexities, guiding mitigation and resilience-building to protect humanity's future.

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Table of contents

Abbreviations and definitions	3
Introduction	4
Part 1: existing and upcoming work in the subfield	
1. A. Literature review	
Brief literature review of the nuclear winter field	5
Nuclear winter-literature on TSC	6
1. B. Expert elicitation: ongoing and upcoming projects	9
Rutgers University - Alan Robock and Brian Toon	10
Aotearoa New Zealand Catastrophe Resilience Project (NZcat) - Matt Boyd	10
IIASA - Christian Folberth	12
National Academies - Channing Arndt	13
Alliance to Feed the Earth in Disasters (ALLFED) - Michael Hinge	14
Part 2: Comparative Analysis	
2. A. Geographical aspects	17
Discussion on specificity	17
Pinch and choke points in global supply chains	17
2. B. Politico-economic aspects	19
Capacity	19
Human capacity	19
Production capacity	20
Infrastructure capacity	21
Incentives	23
International Relations Theory	24
Market dynamics and economic price theory	25
2. C. Multidisciplinary aspects	25
Black swans and NWTSC	26
Intangibles	27
Multidisciplinary lessons from Disaster Risk Reduction	28
Historical approaches	30
Concluding remarks	32
References	34

Abbreviations and definitions

ASRS: Abrupt Sunlight Reduction Scenario

A scenario in which significant amounts of sun radiation does not reach the earth's surface, as atmospheric circumstances cause it to be blocked out. ASRS includes the aftermath of not only nuclear winters, but also supervolcanic eruptions or smaller asteroid impacts.¹

DRR: Disaster Risk Reduction

ERS: Existential Risk Studies

ESR assesses potential catastrophes posing existential threats to humanity and explores ways to predict, prevent, or mitigate them.²

Interdisciplinarity and multidisciplinary

Interdisciplinarity and multidisciplinary share the common goal of integrating knowledge from multiple fields; however, interdisciplinarity emphasises the synthesis of diverse disciplines into a unified approach, while multidisciplinary involves experts from different fields working in parallel within their own disciplinary frameworks.³

NWTSC: Trade and Supply Chains in Nuclear Winters

NWTSC, a new acronym suggested in this publication, refers to the proposed research field within nuclear winter research that involves researching TSC in nuclear winter scenarios .

Resilience

Generally speaking, resilience refers to a system's aptness to endure different disturbances, bounce back from them, and still maintain its identity.⁴

TSC: Trade and Supply Chains

Merged together as TSC, trade here refers to the global exchange of goods and services⁵, whilst supply chains are the complex systems and processes that enable the production and distribution of these goods and services.⁶ This report focuses on the goods and services essential to feeding the world's population and avoiding societal collapse.

¹ Pham, A., García, J.B., Vojtech Brynych, Ratheka Stormbjorne, Pearce, J.M. and Denkenberger, D. (2022).

² Cremer, C.Z. and Kemp, L. (2021).

³ Toš, I. (2021).

⁴ Kemp, L. and Cline, E.H. (2022).

⁵ Olson, C. D. (1985).

⁶ Investopedia. (2023).

Introduction

Solid evidence suggests that the greatest threat to humanity associated with nuclear war arises not from the exchange itself but from the ensuing nuclear winter (Xia et al. 2022; Jägermeyr et al. 2020; Coupe et al. 2019). This risk encompasses mass starvation due to crop failures and potential societal or civilisational collapse. While most existing nuclear winter literature has provided accurate projections of global crop failure arising from certain quantities of debris in the stratosphere, significant gaps exist in understanding the quantities lofted from scenarios of nuclear detonations at one end of the causal chain, and the numbers of fatalities and other impacts on human societies at the other. Unfortunately, our reliance on global trade and supply chains (TSC) for food has been largely neglected in this field. This lack of research on the intersection between Nuclear Winter scenarios, and Trade and Supply Chains (NWTSC) could lead to overlooking a critical factor in assessing the nature of the overall global systemic risk humanity is facing.

Despite limited existing literature, a growing number of experts are recognizing the importance of NWTSC in assessing impact. Several large-scale research projects are now underway that are likely to include attempts to address these dynamics. This report aims to lay a qualitative foundation for these and other relevant projects, thus contributing to the emerging sub-field of NWTSC and emphasising the significance of incorporating relevant aspects and perspectives needed to disentangle the complex systems in question. Focusing on moderate nuclear winters (5-37 Tg soot in the atmosphere), the report unfolds in two parts: The first part examines the historical and current status of the NWTSC subfield in two sections. The first section provides a brief literature review of nuclear winter research and a systematic review of existing NWTSC literature. The second section features interviews with experts from the ongoing projects mentioned above. In three sections, Part 2 looks forward, focusing on politico-economic, geographic, and multidisciplinary considerations for future NWTSC research projects. The first section uses a dualistic approach to economic considerations, examining trading capacity and incentives as constituents of TSC in a moderate nuclear winter scenario. The second section discusses scenario-specific geographic factors, exemplified by pinch- and chokepoints in global trade. The final section emphasises the value of transdisciplinary methods and proposes diverse disciplines, approaches, and perspectives to better understand the systemic risk in question, hunt black swans, and enrich the NWTSC subfield.

Part 1: existing and upcoming work in the subfield

1. A. Literature review

Brief literature review of the nuclear winter field

Nuclear winter, first explored by climatologists like Crutzen and Birks (1982), and later Turco et al. (1983, 1990), arises from the highly flammable nature of countervalue nuclear detonations in urban areas. Firestorms, triggered by the initial fireball and driven by industrial materials such as fuel, would burn building materials and other anthropocentric objects, to release massive amounts of soot into the atmosphere. In moderate nuclear winter scenarios, this would block sunlight and cause a prolonged, ozone-damaging, winter-like climate for about a decade (Xia et al. 2022).

Nuclear winter theory, which emerged over 40 years ago, faced early scepticism, not least due to limited computational power in the 1980s (Robock et al. 2023). Scholars like Kearny questioned the accuracy of early estimations, particularly regarding fire sizes and soot levels (1987). Doubt also arose about soot reaching the stratosphere in sufficient quantity. In 1991, scepticism grew when massive Kuwaiti oil fires, producing significant soot, didn't cause substantial sunlight blocking (Sagan 1996: 257). These debates led to political polarisation in the field. While nuclear winter theory may have played a role in ending the Cold War (Robock et al. 2023), interest waned in the 1990s and early 2000s as nuclear war became less prominent. A resurgence occurred after 2007 with a study modelling a regional nuclear war between India and Pakistan (Robock et al. 2007).

The results of this and other climatic modelling of sunlight and temperature reduction in Abrupt Sunlight Reduction Scenarios (ASRS) following different nuclear exchange scenarios, have prompted an increase in research on the associated starvation risk. This includes not only crop modelling with the aim of understanding the scale of crop reduction, but also mitigation strategies such as resilient food research. The organisation Alliance to Feed the Earth in Disasters (ALLFED) has made important contributions on a range of sub-topics related to nuclear winters and global food resilience more broadly. Researching ASRS-scenarios, they are measuring the world's food production capability in terms of calorie production (Rivers et al. 2022). This framework has proved useful for conceptualising food security since the publication of *Feeding Everyone, No Matter What*, a book co-authored by ALLFED's co-founder David Denkenberger, in which ASRS and resilient global food systems are discussed (2014). In the last few years, three pieces on nuclear winter and food security have been particularly influential. In 2019, Coupe et al. published a paper in which a Russo-American nuclear war was modelled climatologically, followed by

Jägermeyr et al. (2020), who modelled a regional conflict between India and Pakistan. This paper will be discussed below, as one of its sections addresses trade. Xia et al. (2022) conducted an extensive modelling project of six nuclear exchange scenarios injecting different amounts of soot into the atmosphere, and used climate, crop, and fishery models to determine how many fatalities each scenario could produce. At the time of writing, most researchers in the nuclear winter field base their work on the findings of this paper (Jehn, 2023a)

Even after the reactivation of nuclear winter research with strengthened epistemics, certain critics and debates have continued to characterise nuclear winter research throughout the 2010's. These debates revolve around topics such as the actual nature of the fires that would arise from detonations in urban areas, the extent to which the soot would reach the stratosphere and how long it would stay there, and ultimately, the relation between megatons detonated and kilotons of soot produced (Reisner et al. 2018, 2019, Robock et al. 2019). Regarding the debate referenced here, Reisner et al.'s firestorm modelling contained errors, however, such as lack of fuel, too strong winds and insufficient duration. The resources spent debating these themes could partially explain why certain subtopics have been insufficiently researched, such as NWTSC. Although less quantifiable, NWTSC is arguably less disputable than the climatological aspects of nuclear winter theory, given our knowledge about both trade and supply chains' vital importance in a highly interdependent world (Sun and Zhang 2021; Puma et al. 2015; Dunphy 2020). Hence, researching NWTSC should proceed independently, recognising its potential contributions to diverse fields and domains without being contingent on the resolution of other nuclear winter debates.

Nuclear winter-literature on TSC

After reviewing the nuclear winter literature, we examine the representation of TSC in the field's recent academic publications. In these works, the assumption of no international trade prevails, as evident in Xia et al.'s discussed paper, and a new paper by Wilson et al. (2023). Conversely, a contrasting assumption of globally continued trade in the face of nuclear winter scenarios is adopted in several papers, notably by Denkenberger and Pearce (2018) and Rivers et al. (2022). Both assumptions are unrealistic and problematic, however, given TSC's relative importance in global food systems. Nevertheless, the dichotomy is a natural consequence of the complexity of quantifying and conceptualising NWTSC combined with a lack of resources in the research field. Nevertheless, the report delves into a few nuclear winter studies that engage with TSC concepts more comprehensively.

Hochman et al. (2022) Economic incentives modify agricultural impacts of nuclear war

A 2022 paper by Hochman et al. was one of the outputs of a more extensive Rutgers University-based project that will be discussed in the expert elicitation below. The

paper's scope is slightly more focused on economics and market-dynamics than TSC, albeit the piece represents a break with the science-dominant trend in the field, thus its findings are important for future NWTSC-research. Focusing on economic incentives that result from a nuclear winter scenario following an Indo-Pakistani conflict, the authors used a computable general equilibrium model (Envisage) to show that farmers and food distributors will be inclined to shift their resources towards production of the most profitable agricultural products to increase profits, rather than producing the most nutrient-effective crops to feed more people. Their model assumes a halt in trade just after the nuclear exchange, and a subsequent slow rate of trade liberalisation over a recovery period of 15 years, which arguably is a more realistic assumption compared to aforementioned research that disregards either trade disruption or continuation entirely. A key finding is that production disruptions cause soaring food prices, limiting consumption, primarily impacting the poor. Following this, three response channels emerge: (1) farmers shift to more profitable crops, (2) land demand shifts to higher-value uses, and (3) international trade helps stabilise consumption. Regarding the latter, it was found that international trade serves as a tool through which the market adapts to change in land productivity. This follows the proposed mechanism in which regions experience different effects and thus seek to trade in order to minimise damage to the food supply chain. This effectively suggests that when the global food system is negatively impacted by regional-specific effects, trade increases. However, this is not true if the negative impact strains the food production of a region to a critical point, in which case the region reallocates exports for domestic use and consumption. Reading the paper, it is unclear how this critical point will be impacted by non-economic factors such as resource availability or social unrest, however. This complex question will be addressed later in this report. In summary, the piece found that “policy lessons derived from a crop model can be significantly nuanced when coupled with economic feedbacks derived from economic models” (p.11), thus highlighting the impact of TSC on nuclear winter crop modelling. As the authors proclaim; “The analysis [...] suggests that preserving the world trading system is key to preventing widespread famine and suffering—a thriving world trading system minimises the costs arising from disruptions to the climate because of nuclear war” (ibid.).

Boyd and Wilson (2022), Island refuges for surviving nuclear winter and other abrupt sunlight-reducing catastrophes

This paper specialises in island resilience, and is the product of a larger resilience project in New Zealand that will be represented in the expert elicitation. Considering a range of factors, the authors apply a mixed methodology approach to identify 8 island states particularly resilient to ASRS; Australia, Iceland, Vanuatu, Indonesia, the Philippines, Mauritius, Solomon islands and New Zealand. Trade is qualitatively addressed for each state, and the trend seems to suggest that the states should be able to maintain some international trade, with the notable exception of New Zealand. New Zealand is also subject to the paper's case study, which asserts the state as

extremely trade-dependent. Trade is furthermore highlighted as a plausible triggering cause of societal breakdown; “our analysis of resilience factors, and the case study of New Zealand, indicate that risks beyond food shortages might threaten the collapse of society, and perhaps even industry or industrial agriculture. These threats are largely the cascading consequences of interruptions to trade” (12). The mechanisms referred to will be discussed in more detail in the multidisciplinary subsection of the comparative analysis below. One final interesting point to note is that the authors highlight the importance of trade in not only food, but also energy, components, expertise etc. The paper is in many ways a pioneering piece of work in NWTSC with regard to accuracy, and should therefore serve as inspiration for further research.

Green et al. (2022) Nuclear War: Are we prepared?

NZcat is not the only example of NWTSC-research in New Zealand. Green originally co-authored this report for the NZ government in 1987, but recently revised it with two co-authors, which included providing sections on trade, transport, communication and health, all of which are relevant for this report on NWTSC. In the sections, the authors discuss the critical role of trade dependence in New Zealand's economy and its potential dire consequences. The abrupt cessation of northern-hemisphere trade would devastate various sectors and affect New Zealand severely. The nation's heavy reliance on imports is evident, with northern-hemisphere countries accounting for over 80% of trade (p. 12). The abrupt loss of these markets could lead to a 40–50% immediate reduction in employment (ibid.). The report's main finding seems to be the far-reaching implications of trade disruption, extending from the financial sector to health care. The health sector, for instance, would crumble due to its heavy reliance on imports for medical supplies and pharmaceuticals. It is suggested that while New Zealand's pharmaceutical industry has expanded since 1986, it may still require policy-driven efforts to stockpile essential ingredients and equipment. The authors emphasise that the collapse of trade would lead to the erosion of the social structure, weakened communities, and plausible spread of diseases. They underscore the need for resilience-targeted planning, including stockpiling essential nutritional and medical resources, fuel and raw materials, maintaining manufacturing processes, and evaluating the feasibility of self-sustaining medical production. Despite its valuable findings, it is worth noting that international cooperation and international TSC-resilience is outside the scope of this report, as it concerns itself with New Zealand's resilience through domestic policy. Overall, the study supplies NZcat's work, and serves as a useful template for geographically specific risk and resilience research on NWTSC.

Jägermeyr et al. (2020) A regional nuclear conflict would compromise global food security

This aforementioned paper mainly considers climatological and agricultural aspects of food insecurity in a 5 Tg nuclear winter scenario, albeit it includes one informative

section on ‘Global Trade Repercussions’ (7074). In the section, the authors highlight how trade poses a particularly high risk because most of the world’s largest crop exporters are disproportionately impacted by the environmental shocks. Thus, while initial crop production losses primarily affect the Northern Hemisphere, the shock resonates worldwide through international food trade. A network analysis is used to study how countries respond to production declines by tapping into domestic reserves, adjusting trade flows, and reducing domestic use. They introduce a crucial food security indicator, the stocks-to-use ratio, which represents a country’s food reserves relative to domestic consumption. The section then tracks the aftermath of production anomalies for maize and wheat over five post-conflict years, showing that global reserves initially mitigate the loss, but by year four, many major producing and trading countries exhaust their reserves. The study emphasises the potential for trade collapse, with major exporters imposing bans due to depleted reserves, underscoring the critical role of reserves and trade in buffering against prolonged production losses and safeguarding food security. Arguably, these findings are particularly pertinent given the relative empirical strength of the model, and they further highlight the need for more quantitative research in NWTSC.

Other published work

Few, if any, researchers within the nuclear winter field would deny the importance of TSC. Therefore it appears normal to find TSC mentioned in a number of works in the field. Including all of these examples would not be purposeful, however, which is why emphasis was put on the four above. Nevertheless, a few other pieces deserve mention in this last subsection. In April 2022, the NZcat team published an informative preprint that addresses trade, albeit in an Oceanic context (Wilson et al., p. 8). The mentioned ALLFED preprint does engage with trade disruptions to a certain extent (Rivers et al., 2022, p. 13), although its methodology ultimately assumes business-as-usual continuation of trade. Finally, Helfand published a report titled *Nuclear Famine: 2 Billion People at Risk?* (2013). The report compiles sources from a range of disciplines including nuclear winter literature, and highlights the vulnerability of global food systems, trade in particular. The reasoning is somewhat flawed, however, and it is unclear how the author arrives at 2 billion fatalities. Nevertheless, it represents one of few existing pieces of work on NWTSC. Auspiciously, nuclear winter researchers are taking action, as several unpublished research projects will consider TSC. The next section will look into these projects.

1. B. Expert elicitation: ongoing and upcoming projects

Based on an analysis of the nuclear winter field, five extensive research projects addressing NWTSC to different extents are currently ongoing, or will be commenced shortly. Methodologically, expert elicitation was considered useful for this project due to the lack of existing literature, but also because a collection of descriptions of relevant projects appears useful for researchers in the field. Based on

available materials, as well as communication with involved researchers, this section will aim to provide readers with a brief overview of objectives, methods and findings for each respective study. The summaries should be taken as interpretation, however, and do not necessarily accurately represent the opinions of the researchers.

Rutgers and Colorado University - Nuclear Conflict Climate Modeling

Experts interviewed: Alan Robock and O. Brian Toon, Rutgers University and University of Colorado

Between 2017 and 2023, a team led by Robock and Toon conducted a comprehensive research project modelling nuclear winter scenarios. In their 2017 proposal, six scientific questions were proposed as critical to the contemporary nuclear winter field, of which 5 related to simulations of potential nuclear wars, fire and soot-related issues, climate responses and ultimately, agricultural impact. Their last question, question F, was the most relevant to this report, namely; “How would the availability of food and water in each nation, including the United States, change as global markets and distribution systems react?” (Robock and Toon 2017: 4). Despite the research question’s direct relevance to NWTSC, two things are clear after communication with the experts. On the one hand, the project produced two useful outputs directly related to this research question. The project significantly contributed towards the trade-related findings in Jaegermeyr et al.’s 2019 paper, as well as the Hochman et al. 2022 piece on economic incentives in a nuclear war scenario, both discussed in the literature review above. On the other hand, Robock and Toon made it clear that their team lacked the expertise and resources to fully integrate the aspect of trade, supply chains and economics more broadly into their models. At one point, it was decided not to continue researching question F, as the economic aspect of nuclear winters ultimately was seen as a second order issue. Instead, they believe that more useful results will be achievable if their future outputs are used as inputs by a team, mainly consisting of economists, to build a more sophisticated economic model. This could be particularly true in the near future, as the team is commencing a new climate modelling project supported by the Future of Life Institute (FLI), that, together with other completed and ongoing modelling projects in the field, will improve the overall distribution, accuracy and credibility of the predictions made in the nuclear winter field. Robock pointed out, however, that the dependency on philanthropic organisations such as Open Philanthropy and FLI suggests a lack of government interest, investment and funding in issues that ultimately concern governments worldwide. This lack of public attention and funding could also partially explain the neglect of TSC in the nuclear winter literature overall.

Aotearoa New Zealand Catastrophe Resilience Project (NZcat)

Expert interviewed: Matt Boyd, NZcat

Both in the nuclear winter field and in ESR more broadly, there are conceptions of New Zealand as particularly resilient in the face of catastrophic events such as ASRS.

This eventually inspired the scholars behind NZcat to initiate the project in September 2022 with a 5-step plan. The 5 steps in the initial plan were:

1. Building a National Risk Profile for New Zealand.
2. Assess the built profile and develop scenarios in a workshop with relevant experts from the international community of nuclear winter researchers.
3. Produce a capabilities analysis using a qualitative survey and interviews with experts and knowledge holders.
4. Developing a strategy in expert roundtable discussions, using the Delphi method, which involves iterative rounds of anonymous feedback and consensus-building among a panel of experts to refine decision-making.
5. Produce a proto-National Catastrophe Resilience Plan for decision-makers, prompting policy-changes and media/public engagement.

Thus far, steps 1-3 have been conducted successfully, and reports from the workshop and the survey can be found on the Adapt Research Blog⁷. Both include interesting theories and findings, and the visualisation summarising the findings from the expert survey can be found below.

Figure 1: Takeaways from NZcat's expert survey on NZ risk and resilience in the context of a catastrophic event (Adapt Research Ltd 2023b)

⁷ [The Adapt Research Blog](#) contains several useful posts relating to TSC and ASRS. In addition to the posts on the [workshop](#) and the [survey](#), posts on [NZ economic resilience](#), [mistakes to avoid repeating](#), an engaging [book review of The end of the world is just the beginning](#) and more relevant topics are available.

Compared to the other projects discussed in this section, NZcat addresses and engages with policy to a larger extent. This has shown results such as changes to wordings in the government's recent National Security Strategy. This should inspire NWTSC-researchers, as it is reasonable to assume that increased communication between researchers in the field and relevant stakeholders in government nevertheless is a positive factor in pursuit of NWTSC resilience.

The insights from policy perspectives inspired NZcat to rename the final output to a 'Policy Agenda Report' rather than 'Response Plan', to avoid giving policy makers the impression of having received a fully developed plan that may be implemented as a catastrophe is happening. The team aims to publish the report in November 2023, but will first organise a webinar with the most relevant interviewees from step 3, thus replacing the initial delphi-roundtable step.

The NZcat team has thus far produced several papers relevant to this report, three of which are mentioned in the literature review. Additionally, numerous blog posts on the Adapt Research Blog provide valuable insights into the research project, as well as ideas highly relevant to risk, resilience and NWTSC. Overall, the NZcat outputs demonstrate awareness of many key aspects related to NWTSC, many of which will be discussed in the comparative analysis below. Nonetheless, the policy engagement appears as the key strength of the project's approach towards improved resilience. In a blog post on what mistakes to avoid, key policy bottlenecks are identified (Adapt Research Ltd 2023d), and in general, their blog posts and papers engage with policy implications. The obvious limitations of NZcat's output is the narrow geographic scope, although much of the findings are relatively applicable to other states and regions. In an almost unexplored subfield, researchers are in no position to be picky about the research available.

IIASA - Advanced ensemble projections for indirect impacts of nuclear war in global food systems

Expert interviewed: Christian Folberth, International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis

Christian Folberth is a researcher at the International Institute for Applied System Analysis (IIASA), and will lead an upcoming project modelling the food systems-disturbing impacts of different nuclear winter scenarios. They will build on the works of Jaegermyer et al. (2020) and Xia et al. (2022), both mentioned in the literature review. Using their in-house EPIC-IIASA model they will aim to fill gaps in the field, some of which relate to NWTSC. The relevant factors that will be integrated into the model include shortages and supply chain disruptions with regard to labour and fertiliser, as well as crop choices and growing season adaptations, which ultimately relate to market and trade dynamics. Fertiliser and seeds are seen as particularly important, but other critical agricultural resources will also be

considered such as agro-chemicals and fuel. The intersection between fuel and labour availability in the context of agricultural efficiency is a key aspect that was discussed, as this will be decisive in terms of how agriculture could be practised in a nuclear winter.

Folberth is a biophysical agriculture modeller, albeit economists will be involved to model the supply chain-related factors crucial to this project. Although the research mainly will make use of quantitative methods and the sophisticated EPIC-IIASA model, it was discussed how the necessary trading considerations imply that certain qualitative assumptions about international cooperation and societal functions will have to be made. Keeping this in mind, this report aims to contribute with relevant methods, frameworks and perspectives regarding the necessary considerations, in the sections below.

National Academies - Independent Study on Potential Environmental Effects of Nuclear War

Expert interviewed: Channing Arndt, International Food Policy Research Institute

Of the upcoming projects addressed in the expert elicitation, the National Academies' recently commenced project appears as the largest and most comprehensive study. As stated on the project's website, confidential information will be used in the first phase of the study, before a second phase will make use of the unclassified outputs of phase 1 to provide a comprehensive report on the environmental effects of a nuclear war (National Academies 2023). In email correspondence, I was informed that the report is anticipated to be published in about a year (Vaccari 2023). Due to the confidential nature of the first phase, committee members were neither able to discuss the study, nor NWTSC more generally. Nevertheless, there are recordings of meeting and gathering sessions from relevant webinars available on the website, with public speakers presenting on a variety of topics related to nuclear winter research. With regard to this report, the most relevant presentation was given by Channing Arndt from the IFPRI, whose presentation was simply called *Presentation on Trade*. With the information from this and other presentations, email correspondence with the responsible staff officer, Dr. Liana Vaccari, as well as a conducted interview with Arndt, it is possible to comment on how TSC plausibly will be included by the National Academies in their upcoming study, albeit confidential aspects remain unexplored and uncertainty thus remains moderately high.

Several of the public speakers in the available webinars address modelling approaches and methods as critical in nuclear winter studies. This is the case whether talks are related to TSC, as is the case with Arndt's presentation, or nuclear winter scenarios more broadly. However, the National Academies ongoing study is not, "conducting primary research, [but] rather compiling and synthesizing existing information in order to make recommendations on future work" (Vaccari 2023).

Based on these observations, it therefore seems as if their report will, among other purposes, serve to assess different options for modelling. In the case of NWTSC models, Arndt suggested that they likely will utilise an Empirical Dynamic Global General Equilibrium model, although it would be hard to determine which of the numerous available options they would recommend. However, points made in the interview with Mike Hinge discussed below suggests that such modelling could be of limited feasibility. Ultimately, this choice will be scenario-dependent (Arndt, 2023). Arndt made a highly contributing point in his presentation that was further discussed in the interview; the economic model itself is insufficient, even when based on correct information (ibid.). This may partly explain the limited usefulness of the Hochman et al. paper (2022). Although the modelling is sound, and based on correct numbers and findings, it appears somewhat disconnected from the rest of the systems, and does not produce the output needed to understand NWTSC. Why? Arndt provides a clarifying answer and solution; we need chain-modelling to successfully understand complicated and interconnected systems. This ultimately requires a transdisciplinary systems-based approach, rather than modelling based on linear thinking. Figure 2 is borrowed from Arndt's presentation, and suggests one way through which such a chain can be achieved.

Figure 2: Example of a modelling chain where biophysics and geospatial science bridges the gap between climate modelling outputs and economic modelling inputs.

At the time of writing, no chain modelling project that would produce the beneficial output suggested in Figure 2 has been initiated. Such an approach thus presents itself as one of the most promising paths towards accurate and impactful NWTSC-research.

Alliance to Feed the Earth in Disasters (ALLFED) - Various projects

Expert interviewed: Michael Hinge, ALLFED

Michael Hinge is a senior economist. In the interview, three relevant projects were briefly discussed, as well as opportunities and challenges associated with studying

TSC and nuclear winters more generally. Currently, Hinge's team is occupied with a project involving the construction of an ASRS-response plan for Australia. Shortly after this project commenced, the team discovered that supply chains would be a crucial piece of the puzzle, and they are now working on methods of conceptualising this vulnerability. One option discussed in the interview was the modelling of a scenario during which Australia is cut off from all global TSC. This would provide a better understanding of the challenges posed for food production and societal function in Australia, on which a response plan could be based. Although their initial work focused on developing a response plan to assist the Australian government, this is being built out over time, and Hinge and ALLFED emphasise the importance of preparedness and response as complimentary for building resilience. A second project providing preparedness recommendations has therefore been discussed, and this work is likely to start within the calendar year. Here, NZcat's discussed title considerations come to mind. Perhaps 'Policy Agenda' would be a good name for this project as well.

The final project brought up in the interview was an envisioned large-scale modelling project that would look at some, but not all key actors in the global food system, and remove certain inputs needed to produce staple crops, such as wheat, rice and/or maize. This could produce findings regarding the relative importance of inputs. One regional selection discussed was Australia, the US and the UK. This approach has one clear strength; as certain attempts to model NWTSC effects on a truly global scale have struggled to process the amounts of data and uncertainties (Hochman et al. 2021), whilst other projects only have focused on smaller sections of the system (Boyd et al. 2022), this limited yet ambitious project appears promising. Evidently, eliminating trade of goods such as fuel and services such as technical expertise and communication would have massive consequences on many sectors in the selected states. The question in focus, however, would be how lack of trade impacts crop yields in the given states. If the model works successfully, Hinge hopes to enable integration of mitigation measures, allowing for the observation of the extent to which different interventions could contribute towards improved food security in a nuclear winter scenario.

Hinge noted that TSC-expertise likely would be needed for all modelling projects. The need for disciplinary diversity was acknowledged, although the challenges associated with integrating a range of disciplines into nuclear winter models remain steep hurdles.

Expert elicitation takeaways - methods and approaches

This subsection does not aim to summarise 'findings' from the interviews discussed above. Nonetheless, having discussed bottlenecks, challenges, approaches and solutions with prominent researchers engaging with NWTSC, three takeaways seem important to highlight. Firstly, more communication between nuclear winter

researchers working on NWTSC-topics would be advantageous. Given the novelty and small size of the field, there is low-hanging fruit to be picked, meaning that all findings hold value across projects. Secondly, transdisciplinary approaches that incorporate humanities, social sciences and other disciplines will be crucial to understand the complex systems that ultimately constitute not only NWTSC, but also ERS more generally, from a number of angles (Marcoci 2023). Such approaches will arguably strengthen outputs with regards to implications for institutional policy-making as well. The third takeaway concerns approach strategies to NWTSC. Unlike what has been done thus far, upcoming projects should adopt chain modelling, in which researchers with different expertises continuously work together on models and methods that ultimately allows them to address feedback loops, risk cascades and other uncertainties associated with the systemic risk in question. Rigorous and impactful research on this global systemic risk will require the assembling of larger research teams from a wide range of disciplines, which consequently calls for more public and private funding and resources towards NWTSC and the nuclear winter field more broadly. As noted by Puma et al. in their piece on the vulnerability of the global food system; “further analyses using the complex systems perspective are needed, so that the resilience of our global food system is improved in the coming years” (2015: 13). Part 2 of the report will highlight aspects from a range of relevant disciplines, to not only provide researchers with tools to understand and address the complex systems we are dealing with, but also to point out important perspectives that ought not to be neglected in NWTSC-research.

Part 2: Comparative Analysis

2. A. Geographical aspects - on specificity and geographically-centred approaches to resilience

Discussion on specificity

The second part of this report will, in the form of a comparative analysis, highlight disciplines, frameworks and methods that hold significant research potential for pioneers in the NWTSC-field. This short section on using geographical specificity as a research tool to manage complexities (Lewis et al., 2020), will be followed by two longer sections with emphasis on politico-economic and multidisciplinary aspects, respectively. Here, we extend the concept of geographical slightly, to include the overlap between geographic- and scenario-based specificities. In the context of NWTSC, as well as in the existing nuclear winter literature, entirely globally focused scopes can appear slightly vague and generalising at times, arguably making the content less tangible and useful, especially with regards to policy (Puma et al. 2015). Additionally, as the below discussion on pinch- and choke points will demonstrate, resilient TSC depends more on certain geographical locations than others.

Specificity refers to either general geographic specificity, which for example characterises the NZcat project discussed above, or scenario specificity, as was practised by Jägermeyr et al. in their study focusing on a nuclear small scale regional exchange between India and Pakistan (2020). In a highly relevant piece on global food systems vulnerability, Puma et al. address the trade-off associated with specificity in research on global systemic risk: On the one hand it appears that more global and universal the scopes leads to more applicable and encompassing outputs, as seen with the 2022 Hochman et al. paper on global economic incentives. On the other hand, increased focus on specificity produces more accurate research, and although the output consequently has limited use globally, it is arguably more convenient for national policy-makers (2015). Furthermore, the same methods could be applied in future research, ultimately allowing compiled research to paint a more comprehensive picture. Considering feasibility, however, a problem with this reasoning is the lack of resources and funding towards NWTSC. Researchers need to recognize this tradeoff as projects are planned and conducted, ultimately considering what approach suits their objective and theory of change.

Pinch and choke points in global supply chains

In the context of NWTSC and specificity, pinch points are important locations for international trade where bottlenecks and general vulnerability risk disrupting TSC

severely due to geographic or logistical reasons. As pinch points represent critical bottlenecks in the supply chain, they therefore pose global systemic risk. Relevant to pinch points and ASRS, Mani et al. published an illustrating piece on cascading risk from lower magnitude volcanic eruptions (2021). The short paper highlights how locations that contain critical systems and infrastructure intersect with high volcanic activity in seven specific instances. It is argued that the seven pinch points pose a global catastrophic risk, due to the potential cascading effects combined with lack of resilience. Obviously, the applicability to NWTSC would depend on the magnitude of a given eruption or nuclear exchange, but with respect to general considerations regarding pinch point vulnerability, the paper's findings are highly relevant. Using communication, transport, infrastructure and climate/environment as key parameters, it was found that global food systems would be severely disrupted, with considerable loss of trade and production. In short, the findings suggest that even a small ASRS event could do great damage to global systems, due to the vulnerability of international pinch points.

In 2017, Chatham House published a report on maritime choke points that convincingly support Mani et al's findings (2017). Whereas pinch points are logistically vulnerable, choke points are entirely geographic in nature and refer to narrow passages such as a strait, canal, or river, where the width is constrained (ibid.). As the seven choke points have strategic significance for supply chains and global food systems, they serve as critical junctures for an extremely interdependent international trade (Wellesley et al. 2017). Similarly to this report, the paper questions how research on food security has focused on production capacity and interdependence without sufficiently considering key vulnerabilities such as choke points. Using the Chatham House Maritime Analysis Tool (CH-MAT), the authors aim to address the extent to which maritime choke points are of importance to international grain trade, by dividing the international system into regions before considering the proportion of interregional trade of maize, wheat, rice and soybean that transits through one or more chokepoints. The findings demonstrate the choke points as critical, strained and vulnerable, which in turn poses a risk to global food security. The food insecurity in question is scenario-dependent and varies geographically, but due to the interconnectedness of global trading systems, it is likely that maritime choke points would continue to play a key role during a nuclear winter scenario in which maritime trade is maintained. The authors stress how anticipated climate change and subsequent consequences are likely to 'strangle' the choke points to an increasing extent in coming decades (ibid.). Climate change and global warming may provide a useful analogy for nuclear winter scenarios and NWTSC. Regardless of the precise applicability of the paper, it is reasonable to assume that the major questions and findings discussed in the paper are highly relevant to NWTSC-research.

2. B. Politico-economic aspects - capacity and incentives as a framework for understanding TSC-systems

Moving from a narrow focus on geography and scenario-specificity, this longer section will provide a non-exhaustive discussion of politico-economic aspects of NWTSC. To conceptualise TSC, we mobilise a simple two-part framework that sees states' trading capacity and trading incentives as the two twin engines that effectively drive TSC on a global scale. Assuming that states, being the main actors in global TSC systems, will continue efforts to maintain TSC-systems functioning, their capacity is the focal point of the section. Note, however, that this framework can be modified to address private actors or the international system more generally. By examining the two types of capacity in the following subsections, identification of critical vulnerabilities is simplified, which in turn facilitates better development of resilience mechanisms.

Capacity

According to the World Trade Organization (WTO), trade capacity is composed of human capacity, institutional capacity, and infrastructure (WTO 2023). The WTO's work on trade capacity does not, however, concern global catastrophic events; therefore, production capacity is added to these factors. Furthermore, institutional capacity is not discussed in an independent subsection because institutional considerations will be addressed in subsequent sections. This provides a more comprehensive starting point for understanding a given actor's actual capacity to trade during a nuclear winter. Given how a nuclear winter would radically alter global trading conditions, the report's conceptualising of each of the four factors will also be different. Nevertheless, the WTO framework is chosen as a base because it offers a systematic approach to understanding and strengthening trade capacity, both on a domestic and international level.

Human capacity

Starting with human capacity, the WTO focuses on trade lawyers, negotiators, and economists, as a functioning workforce and government are taken for granted in their analysis. In this report, however, the concept is extended to include the entire workforce due to the contextual importance of food-production and distribution. Today, approximately 27% of the world's labour force works in agriculture (Roser 2013). Note that this number varies widely depending on geographic and socioeconomic factors, with high- and low-income countries seeing on average 2.76% and 59.80% of their respective workforces in the agricultural sector (ibid.). Taking the other elements of food systems into account, namely aggregation, processing, distribution, consumption, and disposal (von Braun et al. 2021), it is reasonable to assume that around one third of the global workforce is involved in bringing food to

tables worldwide. What would be the state of this workforce after a small or medium regional nuclear war? This question is critical in preparing for the TSC- disruptions that would follow a nuclear exchange. While the number of immediate casualties would vary drastically depending on each scenario, we know that the environmental consequences would kill several times as many over the following years (Xia et al. 2022). However, adaptation mechanisms driven by governmental or market forces are likely to cause reallocation of labour to prioritise food production and management (Jägermeyr et al. 2020). This could potentially increase workforce size, mitigating nuclear winter labour reductions. For future NWTSC-projects, considering both immediate casualties and potential reallocation is important when estimating available workforce.

Although the WTO's discussed focus on specific roles such as lawyers and negotiators is of limited relevance in nuclear winter research, an important general point is made; resilience during a nuclear winter requires access to expertise. In their 2022 piece on resilient island refuges, Matt Boyd and Nick Wilson highlight trade in expertise as crucial to avoiding the collapse of the technological societies studied in the paper (16). New Zealand currently depends on experts flying down from Europe or the US when certain technological infrastructure fails (Boyd 2023). It would be challenging, if not impossible, for states to secure this critical expertise during a nuclear winter scenario. Kemp notes how "societies of the past and present are just complex systems composed of people and technology" (2019). Failure of critical systems facilitating electricity, domestic trade, communication etc. could lead to societal collapse. This leads us back to WTO's focus on state officials with special expertise, such as lawyers, negotiators, diplomats, etc. These positions are important not only with regards to disaster response, but also for resilience-building prior to a catastrophic event. To counter this vulnerability, a promising resilience-strategy would be ensuring physical availability within a geographical area. A secondary approach highlighted by Boyd and Wilson involves cooperation to guarantee expertise access even under extreme conditions when experts cannot reside locally (ibid.). Depending on such 'expertise-trade' would arguably be less secure, however. Overall, expertise resilience presents itself as low-hanging fruit for NWTSC-researchers to explore, given the low cost and potential impact. Furthermore, this priority could easily be integrated into resilience policies and national security strategies.

Production capacity

Production capacity as a concept originates from the fields of economy, business, and management, where it has been subject to research and theorising, some of which could be of use for researching NWTSC (Korpela et al 2002, Elmaghraby 2010, Zepeda and Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations 2001). This report, however, adopts a simple and dichotomous understanding of what constitutes production capacity; inputs such as agricultural yield and extracted raw materials,

together with means of production, mainly manufacturing machinery and adjacent facilities, such as factories for fertiliser, or solar panels for electricity. Given the context of a moderate nuclear winter, it is here assumed that markets have adjusted towards a primary focus on relatively basic needs, which diverges from the WTO's or business researchers' assumptions. Given this scope, two key considerations emerge; what are the basic needs in question, and what inputs and means of production are needed to produce these basic needs? These are complicated research questions that researchers ought to explore in-depth, both qualitatively and quantitatively.

Despite the complexity of the questions, certain answers are more obvious than others. As noted in the expert elicitation, agricultural inputs such as seeds, fuel, fertiliser, water, and agrichemicals will be important in food production. Food production capacity will also depend on the available means of production; even if tractors and other agricultural tools can streamline production, they depend on fuel, maintenance, and expertise. As noted by Hinge, agriculture will most certainly have to return to less technological means of production in order to adapt to the nuclear winter (2023). As food production will be of larger concern and importance, such an adaptation could be successful, however. Of the inputs noted above, fuel, fertiliser, and agrichemicals will have to be produced and traded in the first place. These productions further require specialised machinery that again needs particular raw materials, such as metals and minerals, to be assembled.

It is beyond the scope of this report to model or even explain the complex systems that facilitate the fundamental needs of technological societies. This complexity cannot be decoded in a short comparative analysis, but will require large-scale modelling efforts as discussed in the expert elicitation, as well as the scenario-specific approaches expounded on in the geography section above. Regardless, we have aimed to shed light on important considerations to make, and formulated central questions for research addressing production capacity in a nuclear winter context. Despite its complexity, production capacity is among the most pertinent subtopics in the NWTSC-field, as better understanding potentially could allow us to identify where food surpluses could occur. The NZcat team believes that with the right preparations, New Zealand would be able to export food during a nuclear winter (Boyd 2023), and ALLFED researchers claim that even in a severe ASRS, the global production capacity could ensure enough calories for the world's population (Hinge 2023). More work needs to be done on regional and global production capacity, however, to facilitate tractable research on how we can produce enough to not only feed all humans in a nuclear winter but also avoid societal collapses worldwide.

Infrastructure capacity

The three following paragraphs will brush the top layers of the intricate dimensions of TSC infrastructure capacity, peering into the nuances of transportation, energy, and communication infrastructure and their resonating implications for NWTSC.

Transport infrastructure refers to sea, land and air-based trading routes, as well as the vehicles and fuel needed to maintain global trade. Maritime trade is most important for food, yet highly vulnerable; the established shipping routes might falter, many ports could become less accessible due to climatic alterations, and maritime security could waver in the face of uncertainty. Despite the interconnectedness and global nature characteristic of international trade, regionally specific analyses are needed in order to understand the strengths and weaknesses of transport capacity in different regions. Boyd, for instance, highlighted how New Zealand lacks a sufficient fleet of ships appropriate for international shipping, despite the island nation's dependence on international shipping (2023). Similar hurdles render other regions vulnerable, such as fuel dependency or large distances between civilisational hubs and breadbaskets. Once these and other transport-related challenges are researched and regional data is available, it will be feasible to model global transport capacity somewhat precisely, which in turn would be crucial for developing adaptive strategies.

Energy infrastructure is inextricably linked to the transportation discussed above. Energy capacity further supports critical systems and infrastructural pillars of society, including production capacity. In a moderate nuclear winter scenario, alternative energy production emerges as a beacon of resilience, as solar, wind, hydroelectric and even unconventional nuclear sources hold the potential to illuminate TSC-pathways. Discussing resilience via reduced dependence on oil trade, Boyd and Wilson suggest biofuel and hydrogen fuels for transportation, as well as geothermal energy and small-scale hydro- and wind installations for other energy-reliant purposes (2022: 15). In addition to the very production of energy, reimagining energy usage becomes essential. Energy-efficient transportation and logistical solutions could pivot the course of TSC toward sustainability, ensuring the continued availability of resources. With regard to NWTSC, this would mean decreasing the distance between 'farm and fork', for instance by relocating agriculture closer to highly populated areas, or through cutting the complexity of the current supply chains. Like with transport, energy infrastructure would have to be researched with scenario-specificity in mind. This would allow for analysis of regional energy-vulnerability and resilience, but also expose potentially decisive energy-surpluses, as evidence suggests that some international trade in energy will be needed for technological societies to function in a nuclear winter (Boyd 2022).

Communication infrastructure is tightly interwoven with the fabric of TSC, which is why the maintenance and continuity of telecommunication systems assume a pivotal role. As mechanisms such as trade logistics, supply chain coordination, and market transactions rely on seamless communication, devising strategies to safeguard telecommunication networks becomes crucial. This is emphasised by Green, who discusses communication disruptions and consequential cascading risks (2022: 15).

The section is particularly relevant for New Zealand, as it focuses on its dependence on American multinationals and submarine cables (ibid.). This implies that, as with transport and energy, specificity is important for understanding communication infrastructure and NWTSC. On the other hand, one could argue that most regions will face similar communication challenges, as modern communication infrastructure is globally interconnected and relatively homogeneous. As little relevant literature exists, this could suggest that communication vulnerability is a promising and potentially impactful research-opportunity within the NWTSC field. Relevant aspects to consider include the role of communication in national security strategies, adaptation mechanisms to communicate in disasters, or the resilience of internet-based trade platforms. In addition to high-tech considerations, research into low-tech resilience-building is also needed. For instance, to mitigate systemic risks associated with communication, one could explore high-tech solutions such as decentralising servers or low-tech solutions involving short wave radio communication. Communication will be crucial for maintaining social order during a moderate nuclear winter, however the infrastructural challenges must be overcome prior to the scenario.

Incentives

Despite the numerous capacity-related challenges and risks highlighted above, evidence ultimately suggests that it is feasibly possible to feed everyone even in the case of a severe ASRS-event (Rivers et al. 2022, Hinge 2023). Nevertheless, as stated earlier, both incentives and capacity are needed to support the continuation of TSC. Most of the scholars interviewed in the expert elicitation highlighted rational or irrational protectionism such as export bans or excessive hoarding as one of the largest threats to global food security in a nuclear winter scenario. Irrational protectionism here refers to a situation in which governments restrict or prohibit the export of specific products although such measures are not needed to feed their population (Kim 2010). As Puma et al. note; “[one] should expect that, during the times of actual (or perceived) food scarcity in the global markets, each government’s priority would be the protection of domestic food supply and markets.” (2015: 13). The Covid-19 pandemic and the economic recession caused by the Russian invasion of Ukraine have demonstrated not only how states are inclined to adopt protective economic policies in times of uncertainty, but also how drastically these policies affect the global food system (Benton 2020, Alexander 2023, Sharma 2023).

This report views research on incentives as a key piece in the larger NWTSC-puzzle because the topic appears to be particularly neglected in the nuclear winter field, indicating that there are important contributions to be made. It will not be easy, however; many aspects of trading incentives are impossible to quantify, and as research would be challenging, findings would be uncertain. As such, the trading capacity discussed above is certainly a more tractable concept. Nevertheless, as both pillars are crucial to sustain TSC during a nuclear winter, this section will mobilise

International Relations theory, economic theory, and relevant literature to conceptualise trade incentives, thereby uncovering important alleyways for further research and policy-making.

International Relations Theory

International Relations (IR) as a field has for more than a century tried to predict the behaviour of states, and although the predictable accuracy of IR theory is debated (Hoffman 1959, Lepage and Nincic 2001), the discipline's theories carry valuable insights that could contribute to a better understanding of how states would act with regard to NWTSC.

The first theory that comes to mind is the widely accepted neoliberal institutionalism, which posits that international cooperation ultimately is in the interest of states. Building on this assumption, the theory claims that three factors determine states' probability to cooperate; democracy, participation in the same international institutions, and trade links (Keohane 2011). IR Neoliberalists also draw on theories such as prospect theory and rational choice theory (Levy 2002), allowing for the use of the three factors mentioned above as determinants in models predicting plausible cooperation patterns. IR neoliberalists can thus give us useful indications regarding trading incentives in a given scenario. For example, in his 2017 piece on DRR literature and IR theory, Hollis notes that, in extreme situations, "cost-benefit calculations, transaction costs, interdependence, and asymmetrical risks are highlighted as contributing factors for international co-operation on disaster management" (33). A final usefulness of Neoliberalism is its engagement with legal institutions and the realm of international treaties. Options regarding international law, bi- and multilateral treaties will not be covered here, nor will the potential establishment of NWTSC-departments in national or international institutions be discussed. These aspects could be considered in future research on cooperative trade in a nuclear winter scenario.

In the relevant paper, Hollis also considers realism, the dominant theory in the IR-discipline. Despite diversity and disagreement within the theory, most realists emphasise the underlying anarchical nature of the international system and suggest that the result is a Hobbesian world in which all states are self-interested and strive towards survival in a system determined by power struggles (Donnelly 2000). Both Hollis and Jamieson, whose papers address the same issue, therefore focus on whether disasters increase the chance of conflict, as realism would suggest that unaffected states would be inclined to attack affected states, exploiting their weaknesses (Hollis 2017, Jamieson 2014). Such cascading mechanisms would be decisive and determine the states of TSC in the given nuclear winter scenario. Although conflict analysis falls beyond the purview of this report, realism would nevertheless make pessimistic suggestions regarding NWTSC; parallels could be

drawn between scarcity of resources and political protectionism implemented by governments under pressure.

Other IR theories such as constructivism, Marxism, or pluralist approaches hold undeniable value in understanding the international system, and should be included in in-depth IR-analyses of NWTSC. However, the dominance of neoliberal institutionalism and realism in the IR discourse and international politics more broadly emphasises the importance of including these particular perspectives into predictive analyses of trading incentives during a nuclear winter.

Market dynamics and economic price theory

Above, IR theory was applied to comment on state actors' incentives for trading in a moderate nuclear winter scenario. However, some would posit that economic theory and modelling provide more accurate and trustworthy predictions. Remembering Hochman et al.'s paper from the literature review, there are important considerations to be made regarding incentives and resource-management. The paper suggests that, as societies and markets stabilise after a year of nuclear winter, farmers are inclined to shift production resources towards outputs that are subject to highly decreased supply despite an enduring high demand. Examples of such products include livestock, fruit, and vegetables (2022). These findings raise an important question with regard to NWTSC; should global production of crops and calories be based on a logic based on nutrient-efficiency, or the economic laws of supply and demand? The former dominates most existing work in the nuclear winter field, but arguably, the latter is more relevant to NWTSC, and should thus not be neglected. When considering the possibility of starvation resulting from high food prices (Hinge 2022), market-based approaches appear even more pertinent for NWTSC-research. This is easier said than done, however. Puma et al. specifically notes that we "need to move beyond the traditional aggregate supply-demand approach to better understand the complex interdependencies of the global food system." (2015: 13). No solution to this challenge will be presented here, albeit the purpose of this paragraph has been to highlight the importance of considering economic theory in NWTSC-research, especially when determining and modelling global food production. Although markets will look drastically different in a moderate nuclear winter, the market forces are likely to persist (Arndt 2023).

2. C. Multidisciplinary aspects -discussion on disentangling complex systems and hunting Black Swans

Although the comparative analysis thus far has integrated several key disciplines into nuclear winter research and modelling, significant shortcomings remain. Even extensive research projects that synthesise relevant political, economic, geographic, as well as climatological and agricultural findings could overlook critical knowledge gaps. This can be explained by two complexifying mechanisms. Firstly, as

previously discussed, the systemic risk we are trying to understand and model is highly intricate and complicated. The cascading effects, feedback loops, and transdisciplinary intersections demand thorough systems thinking and sophisticated modelling to properly conceptualise and address. Secondly, highly impactful yet improbable and unpredictable events, known as Black Swans (Taleb 2011), lurk in the shadows. These ‘unknown unknowns’ are extremely difficult to identify or even conceptualise, let alone understand.

Black swans and NWTSC

Despite the challenges, there is potential in the intersection between these two mechanisms. It has been made clear that this report regards large-scale research projects combined with transdisciplinary approaches as the first and most important step towards a better understanding of NWTSC. Furthermore, it is logical that such an approach would be appropriate for overcoming the challenge posed by the first abovementioned mechanism, concerning complex systems. However, we here argue that this approach would be helpful in hunting Black Swans as well, thereby overcoming the second challenge. More specifically, a large-scale transdisciplinary method could ‘paint the black swans grey’. This refers to the concept of grey swans; highly impactful events that are highly improbable yet somewhat predictable (Taleb 2011). Whereas climatological and agricultural research, as well as debate on nuclear winters, largely have centred around proving or disproving hypotheses and theories, several experts interviewed in the elicitation recalled experiences in which their projects took different turns as they researched the unexplored subfield of NWTSC. This seems to suggest that disentangling the systemic risk, as well as ‘grey-painting’ black swans hold substantial potential for impactful research, for which transdisciplinary approaches would be not only useful, but necessary. Although the following paragraphs merely scratch the surface of this potential, a selection of relevant disciplines will be explored, highlighting pertinent findings, perspectives and methodologies for understanding the complex facets of NWTSC.

In pursuit of successfully hunting black swans, the first approach to be explored is Black Swan Theory itself, as explained in Nassim Nicholas Taleb’s book *The Black Swan* (2011). Therefore, this paragraph briefly looks at the intersection between the disciplines applied in the book; statistics, probability theory and economics, as well as psychology, philosophy and epistemology on the other. Although Taleb emphasises the importance of epistemological humility when hunting black swans, he also suggests tools for identifying the highly improbable, thus offering opportunities for NWTSC researchers’ toolboxes. Here, a few tools will be addressed. Firstly, stress testing various solutions through simulation and scenario analysis may prove more insightful than expert predictions alone. For NWTSC, this ultimately suggests mixed methodology. Secondly, building buffer stocks of key commodities, strategic reserves, and redundancy across supply lines and geographies could help cushion against collapse. The final point concerns Taleb’s emphasis on updating. Avoiding

over-optimisation of lean, cost-efficient systems is prudent, as is identifying single points of failure (ibid). Maintaining both technical and psychological readiness to rapidly adapt approaches in response to updated research findings in NWTSC will also be essential in navigating the novel and unexplored field.

Intangibles

In the 2022 report on New Zealand's nuclear winter preparedness, Green proposed a useful lens for examining nuclear winter scenarios. The framework involves assessing both 'tangibles', which refers to material impacts on key systems like food, energy, health, etc., and 'intangibles'; subtle, societal factors such as emotional responses and collective resilience. The authors seek to analyse immediate and long-term effects of many of the factors that have been addressed in the politico-economic and geographical sections above, while also considering psychological, social and other aspects that could significantly impact New Zealand's society and its ability to cope and recover (Green 2022: 10). Below, similar 'intangibles' will be discussed, albeit the section will include a greater diversity of sources and lenses than the New Zealandic report.

There is an intangible question at the core of this comparative analysis: What happens to humans in a moderate nuclear winter event? As transdisciplinary NWTSC-research addresses this question, the following 5-level top-down representation of the human systems at risk could serve as a useful place to start; the international arena, regional arenas, national arenas, the community level, and the individual level. Generally speaking, the report has thus far focused on the two former, as resilient TSC between states is key to avoiding starvation and societal collapse (Hochman et al. 2022: 11). Nevertheless, the three latter levels are of great importance, and certainly fundamental to the complex systems facilitating TSC. If individuals and communities are not on board with the state, regional and international cooperation will be practically impossible. This is supported by Green et al.'s discussed 1987 report, which included a role-play social experiment designed to model New Zealandic community and government responses to a Northern Hemisphere nuclear war. Surprisingly, they found that citizens and the government had vastly different perspectives and responses. Cabinet focused on immediate crisis management, including rationing fuels and medicines, while citizens felt outraged by what they saw as repressive measures. The experiment findings highlight the importance of communication, cooperation, and foresight between individuals, communities, and the government in managing catastrophic events. The findings also emphasise the potential for societal tensions or collapse in the face of nuclear winters or similar scenarios (Green 2022: 16). Although the experiment provided important results, the work's usefulness is relatively limited due to its outdatedness and narrow scope. If similar experiments were carried out today, the findings could together provide academic value not only for NWTSC-research, but for the nuclear winter field more generally.

Multidisciplinary lessons from Disaster Risk Reduction

The report now turns towards DRR's successful incorporation of other disciplines and methods, which has enriched the field in theory and praxis for decades. Scholars such as Green have pointed out the differences between the natural disasters studied in DRR and nuclear winters, and in both ERS and nuclear winter studies, the utility of DRR has largely been neglected (2022: 18). Nevertheless, DRR has been highlighted as valuable and applicable to ERS (Cremer and Kemp 2021: 28). In this report, DRR is included not because of its direct applicability to NWTSC, but due to the field's transdisciplinarity. Truly transdisciplinary approaches are needed to develop useful systems thinking and address the systemic risk associated with NWTSC (Toš 2021), which is why we have much to learn from DRR's diverse incorporation of disciplines.

Although this report already examined DRR's application of IR theory to conceptualise trading incentives, other interdisciplinary approaches to DRR bear promise, especially within the interrelated trinity of sociology, psychology and anthropology. Modern DRR publications draw inspiration from the early transdisciplinary DRR-scholars (Quarantelli and Dynes 1977, Kreps 1984). Sociology was the first discipline mobilised, and with regard to DRR, sociologists tend to focus on phenomena such as social units, mass panic, inequalities and social responses (Kreps 1984, Peek 2021). This brings to mind the social experiment discussed above, which indicated that sociological tools could be useful in researching tension between social units during a nuclear winter.

In the 1970's and 1980's, the scholars mentioned above pointed towards the human dimension of disasters, and questioned the prevalent notion in DRR, that saw physics, biology and engineering as sufficient tools to understand and reduce disaster risk. They therefore called for more political, economic and socio-cultural research in the field (Bates, Dynes and Quarantelli 1991: 288). An impactful answer to this call was published in 1999, with the release of *The Angry Earth: Disaster in Anthropological Perspective* (Oliver-Smith and Hoffman, 2nd edition published in 2019). Although not all arguments and studies presented in the book offer significant value for NWTSC-research, relevant topics such as egalitarianism as a tool for resilience, or the role of media in shaping disasters could provide considerable groundwork for similar studies in the nuclear winter field (ibid.). Psycho-anthropological issues are addressed, such as the meanings that are taken away from parts of human society and existence during and after a disaster occurs (Hoffman 2019). On the topic of nuclear winters and meaning, there is reason to believe that religion will play an important role in a moderate nuclear winter event, which in turn could affect politics and trade. In the aftermath of large-scale shocks, evidence suggests that people turn towards religion in search of meaning (Adeney-Risakotta 2009), making religious considerations important to consider in NWTSC-research. There exists DRR-adjacent work in psychology as well, which addresses questions on human behaviour in disasters (Nashiru and Zhang 2020). Such questions are relatively intangible, yet

important for us to better understand in search of social resilience, be that for disasters or nuclear winters. As Koons and Trivedi note; “Disaster anthropologists have shown that disasters are the visible, explicit result of deeper and more complex processes” (2021: 1).

Turnbull’s *The Mountain People* presents itself as an example of work that could suggest answers to questions and methods. The book is an ethnography about the Ik people of northern Uganda, and provides an insightful examination of their culture based on research conducted between 1965 and 1966. Turnbull portrays the Ik as a once-prosperous people forced into extreme individualism to survive, shedding light on their practices, beliefs, and challenges faced during a severe famine, prompting reflections on basic human nature and consequences of extreme circumstances (1972).

Turnbull’s accounts may seem extreme, but during even a small-scale nuclear winter, similar circumstances are likely to occur in regions particularly vulnerable to food-shocks caused by crop failure or trade disruptions. There is also a possibility of similar scenarios happening in less impacted regions, resulting from the potential activation of destructive social and psychological mechanisms in the face of an extreme situation. Positivist epistemology is of limited usefulness when researching these facets of nuclear winter, yet these seemingly irrational mechanisms could be highly impactful, also with regards to TSC. Willerslev and Meinart fittingly highlight a quote from *the Mountain People* in their 2016 ethnography of the Ik; “So cruelty was with them, in their humour, in their inter-personal relations, in their thoughts and reflections. Yet, so utter was their isolation as individuals, that I do not think they thought of their cruelty as affecting others.” (Turnbull 1972: 260). If similar psychological effects are produced by a nuclear winter scenario, and these effects sufficiently impact relations between societies worldwide, humanity could be presented with an unprecedented risk of value-lock in, in which non-altruistic and protective values are asserted as the global political paradigm (MacAskill 2022).

With regard to TSC, this would plausibly result in extreme trade and migration restrictions, and the potential end of international cooperation as we know it. The topic of migration is itself an important consideration in nuclear winter research, albeit heavily neglected. More work is needed here, as migration patterns plausibly would look different from current ones. On a global scale, we would see refugees fleeing towards states with less impacted climate and agriculture. On a regional scale, societies would risk conflict and social unrest as people flee unsustainable cities in pursuit of resources. The abovementioned lack of international cooperation would then potentially represent a significant bottleneck, and conflict could arise. These are worst-case scenarios, but even if these mechanisms unfolded on regional scales, it could lead to mass starvation and several societal collapses. Although speculative,

such analyses highlight the importance of understanding the social science of nuclear winter scenarios, in order to detangle the systemic risk associated with NWTSC.

Historical approaches

Although history has never seen a nuclear winter and its effects on TSC, the planet's climate has experienced comparable shocks for the past millennia. Furthermore, the complex systems being studied in this report have been severely disrupted in the past. Seeking stronger epistemic grounds for researching NWTSC, the final subsection will explore a few selected historical events, from which important lessons can be learned. Researchers in ESR have to an increasing extent started to understand the value of history in understanding existential risk, with scholars such as Kemp (2019) and Jehn (2023b) mapping out examples of collapse in past societies and civilisations, to better understand the risks we face today. This report encourages nuclear winter researchers to conduct similar work, as it will consider far from all historical examples relevant to NWTSC.

Rather than adopting a categorised framework, a reverse chronological approach will be used in this historical discussion. Starting with the present, the ongoing crisis caused in part by the Russo-Ukrainian conflict is currently demonstrating the vulnerability of global TSC. Although breadbasket failure and grain exports have been in focus, the fertiliser crisis has actually been more damaging, and carries with it more systemic risk (Alexander 2023), thus offering relevance to nuclear winter studies aiming to understand the role of fertiliser in their TSC-studies. Moving on to historic events, the Covid-19 pandemic stands out due to its recent occurrence, as well as its impacts on societies and global TSC-systems. Compared to other historical events, the accuracy and reliability of research is superior, and due to commercial and public interests, numerous publications on risk, vulnerabilities and resilience related to TSC are now available as a result of the pandemic. Regarding the levels of cooperation discussed above, anthropological, criminological and psychological studies provide interesting findings regarding the relationship between individuals, communities and authorities in extreme circumstances (Wood et al. 2021, Murphy et al. 2020, Akhtar et al. 2020). Moreover, papers on topics such as international trade during the pandemic (Coquidé et al. 2022), as well as global value chains in extreme situations (Khorana et al. 2022, Gölgeci et al. 2023) offer useful insight into the mechanisms of TSC-systems after a significant shock. The latter is particularly useful, as it contains a review of post-Covid studies of supply chains. Focusing on Covid-19 and trade specifically, Mena et al. applies robustness (the ability of a state to resist trade disruptions) and responsiveness (the ability to recover after disruptions occur) as constituting a useful framework to think about trade resilience. The high food price crises of 2007-08 and 2010-11 carry similar relevance and empirical value, especially as research on the instances highlights the importance of considering the above discussed market forces as a driver of hunger and social challenges in regions vulnerable to food shocks (Davies et al. 2010).

From the 19th and 20th century, three historical events appear particularly applicable for NWTSC-research; the Second World War (WWII), the Late Victorian Great Drought of 1876-78 and the Mount Tambora Eruption of 1815, of which the latter was followed by the 1816 'Year Without a Summer'. Although the hunger crises caused by WWII often are neglected due to the dominant focus on political and military aspects of the conflict, sources on the extent to which human societies struggled with, and, in certain instances, overcame the risks of starvation provide valuable information. Whilst this literature often focuses on resilience in battle-stricken states in Europe (Maltz 2015, Collingham 2013), the most relevant academic works for this report are the ones studying food shocks caused by TSC-disruptions. Brennan, Heathcote and Lucas analysed famines in nations around the Indian Ocean during the second world war, and their findings show that, in addition to the cynical military prioritisations made by imperial Britain, economic and environmental factors contributed to famines that costed several million people their life (Brennan, Heathcote and Lucas 2017, CEPR 2019). More lives were lost in the Great Drought of 1876-78, however. It caused between 20 and 50 million deaths, and although trade dependency was not a major factor, there is much to learn from the event (Puma et al. 2015). Puma et al. used data from the Great drought and the Year Without a Summer to model how similar weather anomalies would impact modern day global food systems (2015). The authors found that the impacts would be devastating, as the global food supply system remains robust only until the disturbance is a global one, in which case the vulnerability causes dozens of countries to face starvation. The study holds importance for nuclear winter research, especially because the Year Without a Summer was caused by an ASRS. This fact, together with its relatively recent occurrence, presents the Mount Tambora Eruption of 1815 as one of the most useful historical parallels when searching empirical historical foundations to study nuclear winter scenarios with a transdisciplinary lens.

In his living literature review on collapse, Jehn puts forward the question "How deep into human history can we look and still learn something for today's civilization?" (2023c). Deep history methodology is gaining ground in ESR, and ought to be included in NWTSC-research. There are several historical examples of societal collapses that in one way or another involved trade, and researchers aiming to understand the intangible aspects of nuclear winters should embrace the research opportunities emerging from these historical depths. One could argue that deep history research is where the encouraged transdisciplinary approaches cumulate, supplying life sciences with anthropology, sociology, psychology and archaeology, as well as politics, economics and geographics, ultimately reinforcing strategic systems thinking in order to solve complex puzzles.

One published paper actually represents this cumulation, despite the neglected state of the NWTSC and the underappreciated state of transdisciplinary approaches in this

field. In the piece *Social resilience to nuclear winter: lessons from the Late Antique Little Ice Age*, the climatic conditions during the Late Antique Little Ice Age (LALIA) from 536-556CE, are found to mimic predictions for a small-scale nuclear winter, with rapid cooling and reduced solar irradiance. Analysing 20 diverse societies across the Northern Hemisphere impacted by the LALIA, the anthropologist Peregrine found political participation and social flexibility as pivotal in determining a social group's resilience. The study provides an empirical model to identify social resilience mechanisms, and suggests that inclusive participation could build modern-day resilience to nuclear winter scenarios (2021). Similar models should be applied to other historical examples that hold value for nuclear winter research, and more specifically for NWTSC. Examples of historical examples of extreme situations in which trade played an important role include the collapse of East Polynesian societies in the 16th century and the collapse of the Norse Greenland settlement (Diamond 2011), as well as the collapse of the Bronze Age civilisation (Kemp and Cline 2022). Similarly to Peregrine's piece, Kemp and Cline's paper cleverly exemplifies the Bronze Age collapse as a synchronous failure of an interconnected system, reinforcing the applicability of systems thinking and network analysis for understanding cascading crises across complex societies. The authors note that our modern world is more complex, however, and assert that "there are grounds for believing that the larger and more interconnected a system is, the more susceptible it is to a catastrophe and the quicker and more complete will be its eventual disaggregation." (211).

Concluding remarks

This report has aimed to provide an exploratory qualitative foundation for the novel subfield of trade and supply chain research in the context of nuclear winter scenarios (NWTSC). Through a structured literature review and expert elicitation, it was revealed that this intersection is severely under-researched despite its critical importance for understanding vulnerability to nuclear winter impacts and building resilience. Subsequently, central politico-economic, geographic and multidisciplinary considerations were highlighted, examining capacity and incentives as pillars of trade, and emphasising specificity as an important geographic concept to consider in future research.

Most significantly, the report underscored the necessity of transdisciplinary collaboration to map the complex systems involved in NWTSC. Social sciences can elucidate human behaviour and both societal and political risks, while history may provide empirical context. Furthermore, systems thinking is imperative to trace cascading effects and feedback loops across interconnected complex systems. Only through robust transdisciplinary integration and modelling can we grasp these key intricacies. Suggesting tools to overcome these challenges, the report has provided examples of productive frameworks, methods and analogies across disciplines.

Ultimately, NWTSC has substantial knowledge gaps to fill. With nuclear tensions reaching new heights, understanding trade and supply chain risks can help individuals, communities, states and global actors navigate potential catastrophes. Researchers must think holistically and have the courage to update beliefs as new evidence arises. With open and diligent inquiry, we can illuminate once-obscure systemic risks, fostering resilience in the shadow of nuclear winters. The work ahead will not be easy, but the stakes could not be higher. To protect the future of humanity, we must meet this challenge with humanity's full intellectual capacity.

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